

NRIF Ranking, NACC and NBA Accreditation of Higher educational institutions in India – A comparative exploration

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Abstract:

For the last two decades, our nation has endorsed tremendous growth in the count and types of institutions that provides higher education. The need for education and training has become more critical than before as organizations and individuals are now striving hard to meet the competition and the rapidly changing environment. The New Education Policy 2020 has started getting implemented and getting into its real momentum. The NEP 2020 is a brainstorm outcome of a group of visionary educationists which reiterates and assert the need to improve the quality of education system of our nation especially in the Higher Education Sector to have a global acceptance of our professionals. A holistic approach to Quality assurance should layer out all the process in a higher education institution in order to serve all the stakeholders with expected quality standards. A systematic and continuous monitoring of the quality maintained by the educational Institutions is an effective means to ensure overall quality education in the nation. There are various top accreditation councils/bodies in India with varying process and procedures to accredit the academic excellence for different field of study. However lot of unaddressed confusions, concerns and anxieties exist among the stakeholders of the institutions with regard to the accreditation criteria, process and procedures. Furthermore about the relevance and priority also the perceptual distortions extensively prevail. This deliberation is an effort to critically analyse the methodologies of three well accepted ranking and accreditation agencies of our nation NIRF, NAAC and NBA. Their criteria, weightages, reporting, benefits vis-à-vis in the ranking and accreditation process are critically compared and empirical presented in this article.

KEYWORDS : NIRF, NACC, NBA, Ranking, Accreditation

1.INTRODUCTION

A holistic approach to Quality assurance should layer out all the process in a higher education institution in order to serve all the stakeholders with expected quality standards. The success of a quality assurance system depends on the support and cooperation of all stakeholders. Hence, quality assurance should interconnect the strategic management, process management and measuring-monitoring system which interact with each other for enabling the institutions to improve its processes. The Institutions need a common strategy and action plan to integrate its activities and create cost efficiency and competitive advantage. Each Institution is responsible for its quality assurance system and therefore the quality maps are likely to have varying architecture (Kettunen, 2008)

India currently is second largest populous nation in the world, second largest educational system in the world and five years down the line shall be the single largest populous nation leaving behind China. Demographically too India is a nation of young persons with two thirds of population below 35 years of age and should leverage from this to emerge as a superpower and get into the comity of developed nations.

It is something disgracing that as on 2020 no Indian Institution is in top 100 world Class University ranking as the intense focus of most of our institutions are in teaching. There is no much worth mentioning value adding contributions like quality research, consultancy and industry interaction. Lion part of private institutes concentrate for more branches and more seats. Government of India has been giving focus to education sector and had come out with Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan and thereafter Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan. After the success of these two abhiyans in 2013 (The National Higher Education Mission) Rashtraiya Uccharat Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA) has been put into force to improve the quality of higher education institutes (HEI) in India. The minimum eligibility to get grants have become the accreditation for Universities as well as institutions covered under RUSA and also the regulatory bodies of various professional courses have now strictly insisting for the accreditation for extension of approval as well as to seek autonomous status. Multi-multiplication of Higher educational institutions with hidden vested interest of en-cashing on the growing aspirations of the citizens has brought considerable severe deterioration in the quality of teaching learning process over the years. Quality cannot be looked at as an event; it has to be an ongoing process and a persistent chase to achieve academic excellence. It's an ongoing, dynamic and ensuing effort of an institution.

India has one of the largest and diverse education systems, in the world. Privatization, extensive expansion, boosted autonomy and introduction of programs in new and emerging areas has improved access to higher education. As a by-product, it also led to extensive concern on the quality and relevance of the higher education. Indian economy as well as the global economy has undergone change from being agriculture oriented to manufacturing and now is dominated by the service sector which not only is the major contributor to the economy but also having considerable employment potential and growing.

2. BACKGROUND OF THE DELIBERATION

Service sector like IT, BT, BPO, R&D, Consulting, Media, Insurance, Banking, Knowledge management, Internet of things big data, data analytics has lot of potential for employment of professional graduates. Today we live in an era of digital communication and crores of young people are addicted to it. Change is not only permanent but also happening without any hints and symptoms in the fast paced world. Business environments are fast changing and the professionals need to understand it and stay relevant to be in line with it. Self-Skilling, Operational excellence, innovation, being future oriented by foreseeing the up the trends, improve competence and capabilities are the inevitable need of the hour to be acceptable player in the ecosystem.

According to an earlier report by NASSCOM less than 25% of our 10 lakh odd professional graduates passing out annually are employable. In the same track Aspiring Minds' National Employability Report – 2019 reveals that the employability of Indian professional students continues to be painfully low with more than 80% professional students unemployable for any job in the knowledge economy. Contrary to this the students from the institutions highly focussed on the Self -Skilling, Innovation and competence, 46.21 per cent students were found employable or ready to take up jobs in 2019, compared with 33 per cent in 2014, and 47.38 per cent in 2018, according to the India Skills Report 2019-20.

When we integrate many such thought provoking reports on the bedding professional students which ultimately arrowing to the fact that there is a dire need to improve the quality of higher education system so that to ensure our passed out students become aptly prone to match the needs and wants of the corporates and industries. Government of India has ventured into many ambitious projects such as 500 Smart Cities, Make in India programme, Start Up India, national

Solar Mission etc and indisputably there is great need of quality professionals to undertake and manage these programmes. So the Socio economic revolution 4.0 will invariably demand for high quality professionals.

“The survival of the fittest” is going to be the underlying principle of future education sector and the said survival is subject to uncompromised quality assurance in the process and output in an outcome-based education system. There has to be a systematic evaluation and control system in the education system to ensure the quality and standard to minimally matchup with the global standard. here emerges the need to understand about the importance of accreditation of quality revolution in the education system of our nation. Accreditation is one of the well accepted formal recognition of the quality and standard of an educational institution or a degree programme by an external independent authorized agency based on well-defined and documented criteria and standards. In India accreditation for all universities is compulsory except for those created under the act of Parliament as without it no institution has right to award degrees and call themselves as University. Now it has become the mandatory eligible criteria for the autonomous and affiliated institutions too for the extension of their approval as well as affiliation. There are various top accreditation councils in India with varying process and procedures to accredit for different field of study. Below are some of the most preferred and dominant Govt. approved councils, boards and agencies.

1. UGC (University Grants Commission)
2. AICTE (All India Council for Technical Education)
3. AIU (Association of Indian Universities)
4. ICAI(Institute of Chartered Accountants of India)
5. ICSI (Institute of Company Secretaries of India)
6. FTII (Film and Television Institute of India)
7. NAAC (National Assessment and Accreditation Council)
8. NBA (National Board of Accreditation)
9. NIRF (National Institutional Ranking Framework)
10. AIMA (All India Management Association)
11. BCI (Bar Council of India)
12. DCI (Dental Council of India)
13. DEC (Distance Education Council)
14. NIELIT & AKADOEACC
15. INC (Indian Nursing Council)
16. MCI (Medical Council of India)
17. NCTE (National Council for Teacher Education)
18. PCI (Pharmacy Council of India)
19. VCI (Veterinary Council of India)
20. NCHRH(National Council for Human Resource in Health)
21. (ARIIA) Atal Ranking of Institutions on Innovation Achievements
22. All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE)

(Source : <https://www.reviewadda.com/institute/article/77/higher-education-accreditation-board-in-india/>)

3. NEED OF THIS DELIBERATION

Out of all the above mentioned list NIRF, NACC and NBA are the most preferred bodies to accredit the Higher educational institutions in the present context of education system and scenario. However lot of unaddressed confusions, concerns and anxieties exist among the

stakeholders of the institutions with regard to the accreditation criteria, process and procedures. Furthermore about the relevance and priority also the perceptual distortions extensively prevail.

The National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) in India has published the ranking list in various categories for the fifth time in the month June 2020. As usual various institutions of national importance like IISc, IITs, IIMs, and NITs got placed in the top positions. The announcement added fuel to the anxiety, positive and negative discussion, differences of opinions amongst various stakeholders. Some institutions which have accreditation by National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) and Institutions having majority or all accredited programmes by National Board of Accreditation (NBA) didn't find place in the NIRF ranking list. So now the questions like is there any need for ranking when there is an accreditation? Which is easier to achieve while comparing NIRF ranking or NAAC accreditation or NBA accreditation? and which accreditation supersedes in weightage?, Is obtaining NBA accreditation for few Programmes easier than attaining NAAC accreditation for the entire Institution or vice-versa? Few Institutions who figured in the NIRF ranking list last year failed to find their names in the list this year. Only few Institutions have improved their ranking this year while many went down in their positions. There was some hot discussion about the flaw in the NIRF methodology and suggestions have been put forward to fix it and so on.

The author is actively associated in the field of higher education heading academics as well as administration for the last two decades, has taken an effort to critically analyze the methodologies of NIRF, NAAC and NBA, the criteria, weightages, reporting, benefits vis-à-vis compared and empirically present here a macro view of findings and recommendations.

4. ACCREDITATION VERSUS RANKING

In an educational framework, Accreditation and Ranking are not tools to measure the quality to establish a relationship between output to input, but they are the indicators of the degree of excellence demonstrated at different levels of education. Hence, they are assessments of the totality of various quality parameters of education including the input quality and quantity, innovative process and performance, continuous improvement, institutional support, governance and output quality in terms of students' performance, graduate outcomes, perception, etc. Since Accreditation and Ranking are measures of the overall performance and total quality of an educational institution, the scores obtained for all criteria/parameters are cumulated to compute the total marks, grade or rank. However, Accreditation and Ranking are not exactly the same since there is a noticeable difference between the evaluation methods in terms of the specific criteria or metrics used, weightages assigned, assessment methodology employed, and description of the outcome. Here the author is focussed on three prominent ranking and accreditation bodies of India NRIF, NACC and NBA out of which NRIF assess and evaluate the institutions for ranking whereas the latter two bodies proceed with accreditation. The basic commonalities of both aspects and the pertinent differences between them are discussed below to have an idea.

⇒ Accreditation is a process of quality assurance and improvement to verify whether the Programme or the Institution continues to meet the Norms and Standards prescribed by the apex bodies from time to time or not? Ranking, on the other hand is an assessment of overall performance of an Institution and its comparison with the performance of other Institutions.

- ⇒ Accreditation by NBA is an assessment of the quality of a Programme to fulfill the PEOs, PSOs and POs based upon data made available for 3 Years
- ⇒ Accreditation by NAAC is an assessment of the quality of an Institution as a whole based upon data made available for 5-years.
- ⇒ Ranking by NIRF is an assessment of the overall performance of the Institution including its perception as a whole on yearly basis at national level.
- ⇒ Accreditation by NBA awards marks out of 1000 to the Programme and Accreditation by NAAC awards the grade on a 4-point scale to an Institution, whereas ranking by NIRF gives a score out of 100 to an Institution brings out a comparison among other institutions similarly placed.
- ⇒ Accreditation by NBA and NAAC are the measure of the attainment of the set minimum standards by a Programme and Institution respectively. NIRF ranking is the measure of relative performance of Institutions in comparison method at national level.
- ⇒ NBA assesses the capability of a Programme to score ≥ 750 or 600 marks to secure accreditation for 3-years or 6-years, based upon the extent of fulfilment of 10 Criteria.
- ⇒ NAAC assesses the capability of an Institution to score CGPA on a 4-point scale based upon the fulfilment of 7 Criteria for accreditation.
- ⇒ NBA Accreditation is valid for a period of 3-years or 6-years and NAAC accreditation is valid for a period of 5-years or 7 Years but NIRF ranking is valid for one year only.

5. A BIRDS EYE VIEW OF THE EVALUATION PROCESS

NIRF, NAAC and NBA use well structured criteria and metrics to assess the overall educational quality but with varying key indicators, methodology and weightages. Let us first look into the individual criteria, weightage and process.

5.1 CRITERIA, WEIGHTAGE AND PPROCESS OF NIRF RANKING

The National Institutional Ranking Framework is a methodology adopted by the Ministry of Education, Government of India, to rank institutions of higher education in India. The Framework was approved by the MHRD and launched by Minister of Human Resource Development on 29 September 2015.

NIRF evaluation Methodology is developed based on a set of parameters identified as the core contributing elements to the overall quality of an academic institutions. These parameters are organized into five broad heads, and have been further elaborated into suitable sub-heads. Each broad head has an overall weight assigned to it. Within each head, the various sub-heads also have an appropriate weight distribution.

The sub-head scores are then added to obtain scores for each individual head. The overall score is computed based on the weights allotted to each head. The overall score can take a maximum value of 100. The institutions will then be rank-ordered in a particular category based on their scores as “1” being the Top Rank and in an ascending order with highest in number position being lowest in rank.

Figure 1 Five Criteria of NIRF ranking with marks and weightage

5.2 CRITERIA, MARKS AND PROCESS OF NAAC ACCREDITATION

National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) was established in 1994 as an autonomous institution of the University Grants Commission (UGC). NAAC methodology for Assessment and Accreditation (A&A) is more or less identical to the process followed by Global Quality Assurance agencies which include self-assessment by the institution and external peer assessment by NAAC.

NAAC accreditation methodology is based on 7 broad criteria to measure the overall quality of an Institution. Each criterion has 32 – 34 quantitative and qualitative key indicators as mentioned elaborately in NAAC website. Table 2 shows the distribution of marks for all seven criteria. The NAAC Report comprises three parts.

(i) **Peer Team Report which comprises of four sections which encompass General Informatio**, Criterion-wise analysis based on peer evaluation of qualitative indicators, Overall Analysis, which includes Institutional Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Challenges and Recommendations for Quality Enhancement of the Institution

(ii) **Graphical representation based on Quantitative Metrics (QnM) which include a System Generated Quality Profile** of the HEI based on statistical analysis of quantitative indicators in the NAAC’s QIF (Quality Indicator Framework).

(iii). **Institutional Grade Sheet** generated by Software is based on Qualitative Indicators, Quantitative Indicators and Student Satisfaction Survey using existing calculation methods.

Figure 2 : Seven Criteria of NACC Accreditation with marks

5.3 CRITERIA, MARKS AND PROCESS OF NBA ACCREDITATION

NBA was established by AICTE in 1994 and became an independent body in 2010 and in 2014 India has become permanent signatory to the Washington Accord (WA) which recognizes global equivalence of professional degrees. NBA accredits the programmes run by the institutions and insist that the graduating engineers should have the graduate attributes and skill as defined in Washington accord. NBA accreditation uses 10 extensive criteria to assess the Programme. Each criterion has sub criteria as mentioned in NBA website. Figure 3 given below shows the distribution of marks for all criteria.

The NBA Evaluation Report consists of two parts, namely:

- Chairperson’s Visit Report detailed in Part-A, Part-B and Part-C.
- Evaluator’s Visit Report detailed in Part-A, Part-B and Part-C.

It also includes a report on observations highlighting Strengths, Weakness and Opportunities to improve the Programme.

Figure 3 : Ten Criteria of NBA Accreditation with marks

6. EXPLORATORY COMPARISON OF CRITERIA, MARKS, WEIGHTAGE AND PROCESS

It is well evident from the above mentioned facts that NIRF, NAAC and NBA use well structured criteria and metrics to assess the overall educational quality but with varying key indicators, methodology and weightages. The below table provide a glance of the same.

Sl. No.	NIRF Criteria	Weightage in NIRF ranking	Weightage in NAAC accreditation	Weightage in NBA accreditation
1	Teaching, Learning and Resources	30%	20%	18%
2	Research and Professional Practice	30%	10%	12%
3	Graduation Outcomes	20%	7%	10%
4	Outreach and Inclusivity	10%	3%	--
5	Perception	10%	--	--
Total		100%	40%	40%

Table 1 Comparison metric of Ranking Criteria and Weightages of the accreditation bodies

The criteria considered and its weightage in the NIRF ranking process are illustrated in the columns 1 & 2 of the Table 1. The consolidated weightage of the key indicators contributing to

these five equivalent criteria in accreditation process of the other two accreditation bodies (NACC & NBA) are calculated approximately and are made available in columns 4 & 5 of Table 1 for comparison and analysis.

It can be infer from the Table 1 that the first three criteria used in NIRF ranking are somewhat similar to those employed in NAAC and NBA accreditation processes and these three critical parameters together constitute 80% weightage in NIRF ranking whereas the corresponding and equivalent criteria put together have only around 40% weightage in both NAAC accreditation and NBA accreditation. We can make out from Figure 1 & 2 that NAAC and NBA accreditation lookout into some more parameters that indicate the PEOs, PSOs, POs, curriculum, procedures, implementation, teaching-learning process, continuous improvement and outcomes, which altogether contribute to the remaining 70% weightage. So it can be inferred from this simple analysis that NIRF ranking is largely data-focussed, i.e. marks are awarded for only data (figures) uploaded online and there in no marks for any theoretical description, process implemented and procedures. On the other hand both NAAC and NBA accreditation are data as well as process focussed, wherein marks are awarded for both the data uploaded and for the theoretical description, process implementation and procedures followed. However, NIRF ranking is very unique in the assessment process that it effectively makes use of its last two parameters, namely Outreach & Inclusivity and Perception with a relatively low weightages. Especially, Perception plays a critical role, which is assessed independently by a third party in a very transparent manner from the stake holders, renowned academic leaders and industry experts at national level.

NAAC focus on Quality initiative, Quality sustenance and Quality enhancement of HEI. Self-evaluation in the process of A&A promoting objectivity, self-analysis, reflection and professionalism on the part of HEIs. The self- evaluation proforma of NAAC provided as “manuals for self-study” to track out different inputs, processes and outputs and facilitates HEIs to evaluate their strengths, weaknesses and areas for improvement. The self-evaluation process and the subsequent preparation of the Self-Study Report (SSR) to be submitted to NAAC involves the participation of all the stakeholders –management, faculty members, administrative staff, students, parents, employers, community and alumni. Overall it is expected to serve as a catalyst for institutional self-improvement, promote innovation and strengthen the urge to be the trend setter.

NAAC accreditation is distinct from the NBA accreditation process with regard to data validation and verification process. The NAAC software follow a random sampling method and the data for nearly 70% of key indicators are verified and validated in a transparent way which insulate the institution from manipulating the data or documents after online submission and webhosting of the information. There is a key indicator in the criteria to measure the feedback from local stakeholders like students’ satisfaction survey, but there is no a systematic or defined method or component to measure the perception of the institution from independent academicians and industry experts at national level. Further, there is no key indicator to measure the outreach and inclusivity in terms of student count and faculty count from other states and regions in the country. So a NACC accredited Institution is only catering to the needs and wants of local students and employing faculty members within the state. It means that NACC accreditation DVV process need to incorporate key indicators or criteria for measurement of outreach, inclusivity and perception as used in NIRF ranking in order to enjoy the status of national presence to bridge the gap and complete the quality coil.

The NBA accreditation process with 10 criteria focus on degree of excellence of a Programme in an Institution. Here also as in the case of NACC there is key indicator in a criteria

to take the feedback from local stakeholders, but it is recorded only as an observation which make it as subjective and not considered for calculation of marks. Hence, the NBA accreditation DVV process also need to incorporate key indicators or criteria for measurement of outreach, inclusivity and perception as used in NIRF ranking in order to enjoy the status of national presence to bridge the gap and complete the quality coil.

6.1. Benefits of NIRF Ranking, NACC & NBA ACCREDITATION

NIRF	NACC	NBA
Measure of the degree of excellence of an Institution at national level	Recognition of Institution’s performance as well as social recognition	Recognition of a Programme’s good performance.
Great recognition of the level of performance of an Institution	Helps the Institution to know its strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities for improvement	Institutional Programme knows its strengths, weakness, and opportunities for improvement
Credible evidence comparable with that of other institutions nation-wide.	A new direction to grow and identity itself amongst the better institutions.	Ensures high standard & quality education with regard to the programmes in the Institution
Great mileage to the Institution at pan India level to attract students from various parts of the country to improve outreach, inclusivity and perception	NAAC grade is one of the eligible to receive funds from Govt. and other Research Organizations.	Enables better enrolment to the Programme and strengthens Students’ learning and Graduates’ attributes. Accredited Programme has recognition at International level as there is equivalence of such programmes.
A bench mark of performance	Practise to provide innovative and modern methods of teaching-learning and commitment to quality education and excellent placement records	Demonstrates accountability to the Society, through continuous improvement to achieve excellence.

Table 2 Comparison metric of the benefits of NIRF ranking and NACC & NBA Accreditation

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As mentioned earlier the Institutions of national importance and other universities of International standards are the dominating Institutions in NIRF ranking list. Undoubtedly, they maintain a high degree of excellence in education, high quality, holistic and outcome-based education and consequently majority of the graduates of these institutions have a very high demand in the corporates and industry. So, these institutions and their programmes don’t need any accreditation. Now the question arises as do the institutions placed towards the bottom side of ranking have to achieve both accreditation and ranking or anyone?

It is now evident from the former deliberations that NIRF ranking, NAAC and NBA accreditation uses some similar parameters and some other exclusive criteria for assessment and there similarities and differences in the methodology of data collection, verification, validation, weightages assigned to different parameters and ultimately the description and declaration of the outcomes are also substantially different from each other. All these three bodies authorised to rank and accredit are distinctive in nature and not competitors to each other, but their process and outcome provide multiple benefits to the Institutions as mentioned in Table 2. So, it advisable to institutions placed towards the bottom side of ranking to achieve all the three distinct recognitions, phase by phase successively, in order to add colours in their folklore and achieve fame.

After a thorough study and understanding the author infers that the level of efforts and compliance of necessities to achieve each of the above said recognitions differ. It is comparatively tough to achieve a better ranking in NIRF ranking relative to achieve the NACC accreditation which in turn may be relatively tough to achieve as compared to NBA Accreditation. The process of NBA accreditation focuses on a specific programme in an Institution that offers many programmes and courses. The Department that offers that specific Programme can wholly focus on it and can systematically plan to improve the input, process and outcome of the Programme over a period of 3-years and thus it will be comfortable to achieve NBA accreditation for that Programme either for 3-years or for 6-years depending upon the overall mark obtained. It shows that good institutions with wonderful infrastructure, student and faculty quality and numbers automatically focus on imparting outcome-based education naturally achieve NBA accreditation for one or more programmes. On contrary to this some institutions focus on to somehow achieve this recognition through any means may engage into manipulations and misappropriations in various aspects like interdepartmental transfer of faculties or maintain the faculties on roll with a retention salary to comply the faculty -student ratio to achieve the minimum required scores. Few institutions resort to manipulate the stakeholders presented in front of the NBA evaluators to give very positive feedback and thus adulterate the process. There are institutions try to fabricate the required documents for a period of 2-3 years with the help of some consultants and somehow achieve the minimum mark to secure the accreditation. Such institutions thereafter may not maintain any quality parameters in letter and spirit and they are not into long-standing quality. Further, the NBA assessment and accreditation process lacks the independent verification and validation in terms of the transparent third-party feedback and perception. So the author is recommended to incorporate key indicators or criteria for measurement of perception as used in NIRF ranking in the NBA accreditation DVV process to get independent and true opinion on the overall quality of the Programme being accredited.

An Institution need to work continuously at least for five years with Quality Initiatives, Quality Sustenance and Quality Enhancement in academic performance and activities in the campus to get accredited by NACC. There are Institutions who fail to achieve or achieve B+ or less grade in the NACC accreditations or may secure NBA accreditation but fail to get accredited by NACC. It is not that easy to improve the overall quality of an Institution relatively improve the quality of a programme. There are exceptional cases where the Institutions have got accredited by NACC but fail to achieve NBA accreditation. It is a generally accepted fact that achieving NBA accreditation is relatively easier as compared to achieving NAAC accreditation. As in the case of NBA, NACC also lacks the independent verification and validation in terms of the transparent third-party feedback and perception. So the same recommendation to incorporate key indicators

or criteria for measurement of perception as used in NIRF ranking is applicable in NACC accreditation process too.

Institutions undoubtedly need to comply with all the key indicators in the criteria of NACC and NBA for achieving NIRF ranking too, but NIRF ranking process extend an additional pitch in respect of Outreach, Inclusivity and Perception which exhibits status of national presence for the institutions. The NIRF data verification and validation is coordinated by NBA office and entirely carried out by the third party without any influence from the institutions. Whereas in NAAC and NBA assessment and accreditation processes, the inspection and verification is done at the site and sometimes there may be a chance for the institutions to influence the assessment. The above said factors clearly indicate a fact that NIRF ranking is relatively difficult for an institution, as compared to achieving NAAC accreditation and NBA accreditation. So I conclude with a precise statement that for any institution for quality compliance and efforts to achieve NIRF ranking is relatively tougher than required to achieve NAAC accreditation, which in turn tougher than required to achieve NBA accreditation. The author formulated a conceptual frame work as below to establish an operational cum priority relationship among these three highly relevant ranking and accreditation process with respect to the academic institutions.

Figure 4 : Conceptual framework to establish relationship among NIRF, NACC & NBA

In the present context of the new education policy is yet to take its momentum, the content of which clearly reiterate that the Institutions with systematic governance with transparent process and procedures, long term visions with commitment to impart uninterruptedly good quality outcome based education and dynamic actions to ensure improvement in all possible domains to achieve excellence can only survive in the field. NBA accreditation helps institutions to continuously achieve excellence of one or more Programmes, and NAAC accreditation and NIRF ranking help Institutions in achieving excellence at national level. So, to be the forerunner and trend setter in the field of education, the institutions need to focus to couple and crank carefully with long term vision the NIRF, NACC and NBA process wheels as shown in the Figure 4.

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